

CCG POLICY BRIEF

Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling: Wind Power

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Summary

Wind power is a proven, mature technology that will play a substantial role in the global energy transition, offering low-cost, scalable electricity that (alongside solar power) is likely to supply a substantial portion of future energy demand. Many countries have made wind power a significant part of their energy and climate strategies, and policymakers across the globe have developed robust policy frameworks to support its rapid deployment.

The formulation of these strategies relies on technical insights gained from energy system models (ESMs), such as OSeMOSYS. However, the decarbonisation pathways generated by ESMs are very sensitive to assumptions over the relative costs of generation technologies, especially wind energy. In countries with limited or no experience with its deployment, there are substantial challenges in selecting accurate cost assumptions to use in ESMs, which if not handled effectively could impair the usefulness of these insights. Here, we discuss how global ranges taken from the open literature could be used to define and justify assumptions regarding the cost of wind power.

Key Policy Recommendations

- The sensitivity of ESMs to the costs of wind power needs to be accounted for when used to provide technical insights for policy frameworks and/or Nationally Determined Contributions.
- Academic researchers, government ministries, and other stakeholders operating in countries which lack empirical data on the costs of deploying wind power need to clearly present and justify cost assumptions used for ESMs.
- Global cost ranges from the open literature can be a useful tool to situate cost assumptions for ESMs but are not a substitute for direct engagement with local developers and industry stakeholders.

Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling of Wind Power

Introduction

Wind power will play an important role to play in the decarbonisation of the global energy system by providing a cheap, scalable source of low-carbon electricity across the globe, particularly in the case of onshore wind. The International Energy Agency predicts in its Net Zero Scenario that the total installed onshore and offshore wind capacity globally could more than triple to 2,742 GW in 2030 from an existing 902 GW in 2022 [1]. With advancements in technology and rapidly decreasing costs, wind power has emerged as one of the most accessible and scalable renewable energy solutions. Alongside solar PV and electric vehicles, it is expected to be one of the key technologies for the energy transition.

Despite its rapid deployment and increased maturity over the last two decades, there is still substantial uncertainty over the future costs of electricity from wind power, especially in countries without any empirical data and/or prior deployment of utility-scale wind (either onshore or offshore). The total installed costs for utility-scale onshore wind reported by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) for 2022 varied from a low of USD 1,052/kW in China to a high of USD 3,521/kW in Japan [2], a ratio of over 3.0. The costs of offshore wind varied even more substantially, from USD 2,128/kW to USD 13,136/kW in 2022 [2], a ratio of over 6. These ranges highlight the care needed when drawing cost assumptions from empirical data for wind power deployment from other projects or countries.

This policy brief outlines a curated dataset that presents global ranges of the technoeconomic parameters (eg total installed cost, operating costs, operational lifetimes) which are key to modelling the cost of wind power, drawn from the open and grey literature. The aim of this brief is to discuss the challenges around data availability for wind power, especially in the Global South, whilst providing energy system modellers and other stakeholders with a method of situating and justifying their cost assumptions in the absence of empirical data.

Drawing upon the existing literature base

Technoeconomic data on wind power were gathered to inform the assumptions used in large-scale energy systems modelling tools such as the OSeMOSYS [3]. Relevant data were collected from websites, reports, academic articles, and databases of national and international organisations. The data covers range of parameters needed for the technoeconomic analysis of wind power, including operating costs, capital costs, construction times and total operational lifetime.. The dataset has been made openly accessible in the Zenodo Data Repository and can be accessed via the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/10890362>.

Global current capital costs for wind power

Error! Reference source not found. shows the range of overnight capital costs for the deployment of wind power, taken across 2020–2024. The costs extracted from the open literature between 2020–2024 show substantial variation, with a median value of 1,572 and 3,487/kW for onshore and offshore wind, respectively. Data that were found in the open literature were predominantly from countries in North America, Europe, and some parts of Asia, with substantial data gaps for the rest of the world.

Figure 1: Range of a) capital costs and b) fixed operating costs, for onshore and offshore wind farms in 2020–2024, with costs stated in 2023 US dollar terms. The lower and upper bounds of each shaded box represent the lower and upper quartile of the data (25th and 75th percentile respectively), with the central line representing the median. Whiskers represent the range of values falling within 1.5 times the inter-quartile range, and outliers are shown with diamonds. The 25th, 50th and 75th percentile values are written to the left of each bar.

Using global ranges to address empirical data gaps

Onshore wind will play an important role globally in supporting the transition to a clean energy system, with deployment expected to grow rapidly across the world (especially in the Global South where there has been limited deployment so far). The International Renewable Energy Agency estimates in its 2019 Future of Wind report that onshore wind in the Middle East and Africa needs to increase more than tenfold from 6 GW in 2018 to 84 GW in 2030, displacing both natural gas and coal-fired power generation [4].

Understanding the current and future costs of deployment will be key to the effective design of policy support and the development of appropriate integrated energy and climate strategies. Error! Reference source not found. **Error! Reference source not found.** Figure 2 shows the range of capital costs between 2020–2024 by region (where available) and projected global costs in 2030 and 2050, whilst Figure 3 shows the range of financing costs reporting by world region. Given the capital intensive nature of wind power, the cost of electricity is highly dependent on both the financing costs and upfront capital costs, which as demonstrated in both Figures can vary substantially. Data gaps therefore create significant difficulties for energy system modellers around the selection and justification of cost assumptions for wind power, as incorrect assumptions can lead to substantially different conclusions on the cost of electricity.

Figure 2: Range of capital costs for onshore wind farms in a) 2020-2024 for each world region, where available, and b) global projections for 2030 and 2050. Costs are stated in 2023 US dollar terms.

Figure 3: Range of financing costs for onshore wind power in each world region, where available, in 2020-2024.

In countries and regions with limited deployment of wind power, it is important for energy system modellers to clearly highlight the cost assumptions used in power and energy system modelling, as the decarbonisation pathways and technical insights developed from modelling may be highly sensitive to the costs of wind power. Transparent documentation of assumptions and methodologies will also increase confidence in the modelling results, facilitating informed decision-making by policymakers and other stakeholders. The ranges presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** are intended to serve as a useful tool to situate assumptions in energy system models (ESMs) for these countries against empirical data taken from other countries and regions, addressing the data gaps whilst still providing robust technical insights to support the development of energy and climate strategies by policymakers.

Prioritising transparency and data sharing amongst stakeholders will also be essential to enhance the accuracy and utility of ESMs. By openly sharing data and methodologies, academic researchers, government ministries, industry professionals, and other stakeholders can work collaboratively to address data gaps, compare and contrast their assumptions, and so improve the reliability of energy system modelling outcomes. Given the potential sensitivity of ESMs to the costs of wind power, energy system modellers should also conduct sensitivity tests to assess the robustness of their models. Understanding how variations in cost assumptions impact model outcomes will be crucial for making informed decisions and developing resilient energy transition pathways, and situating their assumptions against the global cost curve could be a useful way of exploring model sensitivities.

However, whilst the global ranges from the open literature presented in this work can provide valuable insights and offer a way to address empirical data gaps, they should complement, not replace, direct engagement with private sector stakeholders. Collaborating with industry partners can enrich data collection efforts and ensure that ESMs accurately reflect real-world conditions and the true costs of wind power.

Conclusions

Addressing the challenges of data availability for wind power will be critical to accelerating the energy transition, particularly in countries in the Global South where there is limited experience with the deployment of wind power. By recognising the sensitivity of ESMs to assumptions over the costs of wind power, prioritising transparency and data sharing, and justifying cost assumptions in regions with limited empirical data, stakeholders can enhance the accuracy and reliability of the scenarios generated from ESMs. This will help ensure their accuracy, utility, and relevance to policy. Whilst global ranges from the open literature can serve as useful reference points, engaging with private sector stakeholders will be essential to understanding and capturing the complexities of real-world deployment scenarios.

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